

Studies in similar lines are in progress.

Acknowledgement

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Isolation of Some Sterol Glucosides and a Triterpene from *Mollugo Hirta*

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THE isolation of new triterpenoid saponin from *M. hirta* was reported earlier¹⁻⁴. The present paper reports the isolation of a mixture of two sterolglucosides and oleanolic acid from the same source.

The ethanolic extract of the air-dried powdered plant was concentrated and the glycosides were precipitated with ether and hydrolysed with acid in the usual way (*loc. cit.*) for 20 min. The aglycones were taken up in chloroform and separated into neutral and acidic fractions. The neutral fraction was chromatographed over a column of silica gel. Chloroform: ethanol (90:10) eluate furnished a crystalline compound, m.p. 272°-76°(d) which showed a single spot in t.l.c. over silica gel G as well as silica gel G impregnated with aqueous AgNO₃ solution (12.5%). It gave violet → green colour in the Liebermann Burchard test indicating it to be a sterol. Moreover, its mass spectrum showed peaks at m/e 574 (C₃₅H₅₈O₆) and 576 (C₃₅H₆₀O₆) besides two other

peaks at m/e 412 (C₂₉H₄₈O) and 414 (C₂₉H₅₀O) which could be explained as due to the loss of glucosyl moiety (C₆H₁₁O₅) from the molecular ions with transfer of one H-atom as shown here:

and this suggested the compound to be a mixture of two sterol glucosides.

The above mixture of sterol glucosides furnished on acid hydrolysis, glucose (identified by paper chromatography) and a mixture of two sterols which showed two spots in t.l.c. over silica gel G impregnated with silver nitrate solution and the spots corresponded to those of β -sitosterol and γ -sitosterol respectively. The above mixture was acetylated and column chromatography of the product furnished β -sitosterol acetate and γ -sitosterol acetate, identified by comparisons of m.p. mixed m.p. and I.R. spectra with authentic samples. So the glucoside isolated by us is a mixture of the glucosides of β -sitosterol and γ -sitosterol.

The acid saponin fraction was esterified with diazomethane and chromatographed over silica gel. Benzene: chloroform (2:1) eluate furnished a compound m.p. 198°-99°, which formed an acetate, m.p. 220°-21°. These were identified as methyl oleanolate and acetyl methyl oleanolate respectively by comparison of m.p., mixed m.p. and I.R. spectra with the authentic samples.

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